

Multi-Sensor System for Pipe Inspection using an Autonomous Hybrid Aerial Robot

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Abstract—The use of aerial robots for the inspection of Oil&Gas production plants has considerably evolved in recent years. This article presents an aerial hybrid robotic system with the ability to autonomously land on the pipe to be inspected, so it can deploy a satellite crawler robot for accurate inspections. In order to ensure safe autonomous navigation in unknown environments, the aircraft is equipped with a redundant localization system. A sensor fusion of multiple pose estimation sources is performed to estimate the aircraft pose in a robust and efficient manner. Regarding the detection of the pipe to land on, its position is estimated by using the point cloud of an on-board camera. This paper presents both the localization and the pipe detection modules. Finally, successful experimental results carried out in an indoor environment are shown, being all computations performed on board the aerial platform. A video of the results including a fully autonomous mission can be accessed at <https://youtu.be/N3ZGVuDy1qA>.

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, one of the fields of application in which Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) are growing exponentially is the inspection and maintenance of industrial environments and civil infrastructure. These environments range from refineries to production plants, tunnels or viaducts [1] [2].

In Oil&Gas production plants, most of the components are often subject to degradation. This is because of exposure to the environment or products within the production process. Excessive pipe corrosion may lead to accidents, including failures with explosions and/or the release of toxic products. This has an impact on safety for workers, the environment, and the availability of the plant itself.

For these reasons, it is necessary to carry out regular inspections of the production plants. Such inspections can be dangerous for the workers, since they are exposed to hazards such as high-temperature surfaces, toxic products, or works at height. In addition to the significant safety issues, these inspections are costly for the production plants to carry out.

In [3], a solution for pipe monitoring using a Vertical Take-Off and Landing (VTOL) UAV is proposed. However, the authors only addressed the communication between vehicles and the management of the deployment plan. In any case, they did not perform any inspection or measurement on any structure, such as its thickness or the presence of defects.

A thorough analysis of the types of inspections performed by UAVs in industrial environments is presented in [4]. In the case of pipe inspections, the focus is on the inspection of buried pipes and the detection of thickness loss.

Fig. 1. Autonomous landing performed during the experiments

The novel aerial manipulator proposed in [5] highlights the benefits of the use of aerial robots for the Oil&Gas inspection industry. This system allows taking ultrasonic measurements from surfaces with which it makes contact with its robotic arm. However, the high energy consumption of such operations during flight greatly limits the autonomy of this kind of solutions.

Other solutions propose that the aerial robot lands on the structure to be inspected, in order to save energy and provide longer inspection mission times. The development performed in [6] exposes aerial robot landing on pipes using a soft landing gear and Deep Learning models for pipe detection. Although the autonomous perching on the pipeline has been validated, the pipe detection model heavily depends on the environment. In addition, the navigation system based on the PX4 estimator does not have a high degree of robustness. Therefore, in the case of an internal estimator failure, the aircraft would be lost and the autonomous inspection would fail.

On another level, the necessary autonomous operation of the UAVs to increase productivity in such inspection tasks poses a challenge in the localization systems on which these aerial robots must rely. This is due to the fact that Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) signals may be partially or totally degraded in environments such as refineries, due to occlusions and the presence of metallic structures. Robot localization in GNSS-denied environments has been the target for extensive research in the past decades, also targeting aerial robotics and especially using vision-based sensors for their low cost and weight [7] [8]. More

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recently, there are some commercial options that allow simplifying the pose estimation for aerial robotic systems, for example with the advent of commercial tracking cameras [9]. Even there are fully commercial platforms such as the one offered by Skydio [10], which makes use of several on-board cameras to navigate and can perform inspections autonomously; however, such inspection is limited to a visual assessment of the state of the infrastructure.

This paper proposes a complete system to perform pipe inspections with a hybrid aircraft, composed by an aerial robot that lands on a pipe, and then deploys a satellite crawler robot for inspection measurements. This system has the capability to perform autonomous pipe inspection through its cylinder detection system. In addition, a sensor fusion algorithm for redundant vision-based sensors is presented, so that it can continue navigating even if a sensor fails. This allows the hybrid system to land on the pipe and, while the aerial vehicle waits, the crawler vehicle can perform measurements on the pipe walls. Fig. 1 shows a sequence of the autonomous approach and landing maneuver.

The rest of the article is structured as follows. Section II describes the complete proposed system, both the platform and the onboard sensors. Section III focuses on the perception algorithms used to detect and estimate the pose of the pipe to be inspected. Section IV focuses on the redundant localization sensor fusion which allows continuing the inspection in case of failure of any sensor. Section V evaluates the proposed algorithms with real experiments in an indoor testbed. Finally, the conclusions and future work are summarized in Section VI.

II. SYSTEM OVERVIEW

The hybrid platform has been designed following several requirements to be able to operate in real environments. This platform is conformed by the aerial vehicle and the crawler, as can be seen in Fig. 2. The goal of the aerial platform is to navigate safely within a refinery environment. When the pipe to be inspected has been selected, it is able to land on it by using the aircraft's landing gear. Once it has landed, the crawler moves along the pipe and carries out the desired inspection.

Fig. 2. Render of Hybrid Platform design

In order to be able to navigate safely between pipes, the aircraft carries six cameras on board. Three of them are Intel RealSense T265 tracking cameras, which are used for localization in the unknown environment. These cameras are installed at different positions and angles to maximize the acquired information from the environment, and have triple redundancy in the estimation of the vehicle pose. Then, three Intel RealSense D435i RGB-D cameras are placed also facing different orientations: front, up and down. These cameras are used for obstacle detection, while the downward facing camera is also employed for the detection of the pipe on which the aircraft should land.

It is important to note that all the data from the onboard sensors is transformed to the center of the aircraft, in order to be able to integrate them properly.

III. PIPE POSE ESTIMATION

The main goal of the perception algorithms is to estimate the pose of the pipe on which the hybrid system must land to perform the inspection. The point cloud from the downward depth camera is processed so that the target pipe is segmented and estimated. The algorithm is based on previous work by the authors [11] with some improvements. Fig. 3 shows a diagram of the pipe segmentation algorithm used.

Fig. 3. Perception algorithm diagram

The perception algorithm can be divided into two parts: point cloud pre-processing, and target pipe pose estimation. During the first stage, several filtering steps are performed based on [12]. First, a Crop-Box filter is performed so that only the volume right under the aircraft is analyzed. To this resulting volume, a Voxel-Grid filter is applied, so that the number of points is decreased to estimate the cylinder pose in the shortest possible time. The last step of this stage is an Euclidean cluster extraction, which separates the remaining elements in the point cloud, providing as an output every possible pipe in a different set of point clouds.

In the second stage of the pipeline, the target cylinder pose is estimated. For each cluster, surface normals are estimated using the OpenMP standard [13]. These normals support the estimation of a model using Random Sample Consensus (RANSAC) [14]. RANSAC is an iterative method used to estimate the parameters of a mathematical model, a cylinder in our case, from a set of observed data that may contain outliers. The models obtained with RANSAC consist of the following coefficients: a point in the cylinder axis, the axis direction vector, and the estimated radius.

To check if the coefficients provided by the segmentation algorithm are consistent with previous detections, they are compared with a queue of previously obtained values. This allows ensuring a temporal consistency with the detected pipe and track it in consecutive frames. In contrast to the original algorithm, the cylinder to be landed on can be selected and tracked. This allows landing in more complex environments, where the most centered pipe is not always the target pipe. The full process of pipe detections is shown in Fig. 4.

As previously mentioned, the improvements to the original algorithm mainly focus on guaranteeing consistency in pipe pose estimation. For this purpose, the curvature of the segmented pipe has also been tackled, by using its centroid and neighborhood. To determine these neighbors efficiently, the input point cloud is split into smaller chunks using spatial decomposition techniques such as kd-trees. Then, closest point searches are performed in that space. The method used to estimate the curvature at a point p is to perform an eigendecomposition (i.e. compute the eigenvectors and eigenvalues) of the covariance matrix of the k -neighborhood point surface patch.

In a 3D point cloud a centroid is used to determine the covariance matrix of a certain point. From this three-dimensional covariance matrix, the eigendecomposition can be performed to know the curvature of the surface at a point. [15] The output surface curvature is estimated as a relationship between the eigenvalues of the covariance matrix as:

$$c = \frac{\lambda_0}{\lambda_0 + \lambda_1 + \lambda_2} \quad (1)$$

where c is the curvature at the centroid of the cylinder, and λ_i is each eigenvalue of the three-dimensional covariance matrix, satisfying $\lambda_0 < \lambda_1 < \lambda_2$.

IV. REDUNDANT LOCALIZATION

The other main module of the perception system is the sensor fusion of a redundant odometry system, which allows a robust pose estimation for autonomous navigation towards the target pipe. For this, the three tracking cameras are fused using an approach based on the well-known Kalman Filter [16]. This filtering technique can be divided into two distinct phases: prediction and update. The predict phase uses the state estimated from the previous point of time to produce an estimate of the state at the current time. This phase is

expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k-1} &= \mathbf{F}_k \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k-1|k-1} + \mathbf{B}_k \mathbf{u}_k \\ \mathbf{P}_{k|k-1} &= \mathbf{F}_k \mathbf{P}_{k-1|k-1} \mathbf{F}_k^\top + \mathbf{Q}_k \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k-1}$ is the *a priori* state estimate at time k given observations up to $k-1$, \mathbf{F}_k is the state transition model which is applied to the previous state estimation $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k-1|k-1}$, \mathbf{B}_k is the control-input model which is applied to the control vector \mathbf{u}_k , $\mathbf{P}_{k|k-1}$ is the *a priori* estimate covariance matrix and \mathbf{Q}_k the covariance of the process noise.

In the update phase, the innovation at time k , $\tilde{\mathbf{y}}_k$, is multiplied by the optimal Kalman gain, \mathbf{K}_k , and is combined with the previously estimated state to refine the state estimation:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\mathbf{y}}_k &= \mathbf{z}_k - \mathbf{H}_k \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k-1} \\ \mathbf{K}_k &= \mathbf{P}_{k|k-1} \mathbf{H}_k^\top \left(\mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{P}_{k|k-1} \mathbf{H}_k^\top + \mathbf{R}_k \right)^{-1} \\ \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k} &= \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k-1} + \mathbf{K}_k \tilde{\mathbf{y}}_k \\ \mathbf{P}_{k|k} &= (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}_k \mathbf{H}_k) \mathbf{P}_{k|k-1} \\ \tilde{\mathbf{y}}_{k|k} &= \mathbf{z}_k - \mathbf{H}_k \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{z}_k is the observation at time k and \mathbf{I} is the identity matrix.

In order to extend the filter to N sensors that provide the same type of information, it is necessary to pay special attention to the terms \mathbf{H}_k and \mathbf{R}_k . The observation matrix, \mathbf{H}_k , maps the state space into the observed space. Its dimensions are defined by the size of the state vector and the size of the observation vector. Regarding the covariance of the observation noise matrix, \mathbf{R}_k , it determines how much information from the measurement is used. If \mathbf{R}_k is high, the filter considers that the measurements are not very accurate and further consideration will be given to the estimation of the model used. Its dimensions are defined by the size of the observation vector.

Although this work has used three redundant pose estimation sensors, the implementation of the redundant Kalman Filter can be extended to N sensors. In the following, the main equations for the implementation of this filter and the considerations taken are explained.

Our state vector and observation vector, \mathbf{x}_k and \mathbf{z}_k respectively, are shown in equation (4). As it can be seen, this filter is only used to estimate the aircraft's position, and considers the use of the three on-board tracking cameras as observations.

Regarding the orientation estimation, the Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) integrated into the aircraft autopilot is used. This is because the attitude estimation of the autopilot is sufficiently accurate and reliable, as well as operating at a high frequency, around 100 Hz. This allows to easily synchronize its measurements with the estimations of the proposed filter.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x}_k &= [x \quad \dot{x} \quad y \quad \dot{y} \quad z \quad \dot{z}] \\ \mathbf{z}_k &= [x_1 \quad y_1 \quad z_1 \quad x_2 \quad y_2 \quad z_2 \quad x_3 \quad y_3 \quad z_3] \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Due to the nature of the aircraft motion, the state transition matrix, \mathbf{F}_k , shall be defined from the equation of uniform rectilinear motion on each axis ($x_k = x_{k-1} + \dot{x}_{k-1} \Delta t$).

Fig. 4. Segmentation and cylinder selection from D435i point cloud

$$\mathbf{F}_k = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \Delta t & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & \Delta t & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & \Delta t \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

As mentioned above, the observation matrix, \mathbf{H}_k , maps the state space into the observed space. In other words, it converts the predicted state to the observation vector dimension:

$$\mathbf{H}_k = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ \vdots & & & \ddots & & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

Finally, the influence and shape of the observation matrix, \mathbf{R}_k , is analyzed. This is a square matrix providing information on the uncertainty of each measure. It is also known as the covariance matrix. Any covariance matrix is symmetric and positive semi-definite, and its main diagonal contains the variances.

This matrix is crucial in our redundant Kalman Filter, as it defines which sensors to take into account and which ones to discard. In the case where the localization of one of the odometry sources starts to drift, its covariance will increase. This allows the filter to give priority to the motion model rather than the information received from such odometry source. In this way, a valid estimate will be achieved even when one or even several of the odometry sources have failed.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A. Inspection workflow

In order to better introduce the experiments performed to validate the proposed algorithms, the behavior of the aircraft during the execution of a mission is first presented. Fig. 5 shows the inspection workflow. The autonomous mission starts with the aircraft taking off from the ground, using our redundant localization system as the base for autonomous navigation. After that, it starts searching for pipes in a

straight line from the point where it is hovering after taking off.

Once it finds a set of pipes, the aircraft goes hovering. At this point, it waits for the operator to select the pipe to be inspected. If the operator does not want to inspect any of the pipes detected by the system, the search will continue.

In case any of the detected pipes is selected, the aircraft then aligns itself with it and start descending. Once it reaches a safe distance, the operator is asked for confirmation to land on such pipe. In case of acceptance, a fine alignment with the axis of the pipe is made, and the aircraft lands on it. Once landed, the crawler is deployed to perform the inspection.

Fig. 5. Workflow of a pipe inspection

It should be noted that, although not shown in the diagram in Fig. 5, the crawler returns to the aircraft after completing the inspection, and after that, the aircraft takes off from the pipe and returns autonomously to the initial take-off location.

All the experiments have been carried out in the indoor testbed at CATEC, which houses a VICON indoor localization system with millimetric accuracy. Thanks to this system, both the proposed localization sensor fusion and the estimation of the pipe position is analyzed.

B. Pipe Pose Estimation

First, the pipe pose estimation is evaluated. In order to properly do this, the pipe estimation algorithm must

be decoupled from the relative localization algorithm. For this purpose, the VICON system was used for aircraft localization in these experiments.

This evaluation is based on the measurement of the perpendicular distance from the estimated position to the central axis of the pipe. This is because the goal is not to land on a specific point of the pipe, rather to land on the axis of the pipe. Such distance is calculated as follows:

$$d = \frac{|Am + Bn + C|}{\sqrt{A^2 + B^2}} \quad (7)$$

where A , B and C are the parameters that define the straight line of the pipe axis in the XY plane, and (m, n) are the XY coordinates of the estimated position of the pipe.

Two experiments have been performed on the same use case. From these, the average error in the pipeline estimation has been calculated. It should be noted that these flights have been carried out in manual mode, in order to also decouple the integration of the VICON localization with the control strategy, which could bring oscillations to the platform. During the execution of an autonomous mission, this error is more stable, since the flight of the aircraft is more stable as well.

Fig. 6 shows the evolution of the estimated distance error over time for the first experiment, while Fig. 7 shows the same evolution during the second experiment.

Fig. 6. Distance error from estimated pose to cylinder axis in Experiment 1

It can be seen that the average error in the estimation of the pipe position is less than 5cm, as Table I shows. This allows asserting that in cylinders whose radius is larger, it will be possible to land the aircraft and perform autonomous inspections.

When performing an autonomous flight, the position of the aircraft is more stable. This will allow to maintain low estimation errors over time and feedback to the controllers necessary to land autonomously on the pipe.

Fig. 7. Distance error from estimated pose to cylinder axis in Experiment 2

TABLE I
MEAN ERRORS FOR PIPE POSE ESTIMATION

	Experiment 1	Experiment 2
Mean Error	0.0495	0.0439

C. Redundant Localization

In this subsection, the localization system based on the Redundant Kalman Filter is evaluated. For this purpose, two types of experiments have been repeatedly tested: a squared trajectory, and the execution of the complete mission, i.e. from take off to pre-landing on the pipe (instead of actually landing), return to the take off location and land.

To evaluate the proposed sensor fusion, the *evo* package [17] has been used. The comparison between odometries is made by calculating the absolute pose error (APE). This metric evaluates the global consistency of the estimated trajectory by comparing the absolute distances between the estimations and the ground truth provided by the VICON motion capture system.

Moreover, the estimated orientation is also evaluated through the relative orientation error, even though this value is not part of our state vector. The motivation of this plot is to assess if the orientation estimation provided by the onboard autopilot is accurate enough for the purposes of our application.

1) *Squared Trajectory Evaluation*: During the course of this experiment, one of the sensors failed. This was due to some external problem associated with the odometry of the lower-right camera on the aircraft. Fig. 8 shows the trajectory performed during the experiment.

Fig. 9 shows the APE of each odometry source and the result of the sensor fusion. It can be seen how the proposed localization improves the estimations obtained by each sensor individually, and how it is able to avoid the effect of the failure of one of the sensors. This can be also seen

Fig. 8. Comparison of the position in the squared trajectory

in Table II, where several metrics for each sensor and our fused approach are shown.

Fig. 9. APE Evaluation in squared trajectory

Fig. 10 shows the relative orientation error between the estimated pose and the ground-truth. As it can be seen, the mean error is around 0.12 degrees, showing that the orientation used, which comes directly from the autopilot, is sufficiently accurate for performing safe autonomous missions.

These results demonstrate the correct functioning of the proposed sensor fusion strategy. Even if there is an error in an odometry source, due to the redundant sensor system, it is possible to continue navigating autonomously through the inspection area.

TABLE II
RESULTS FOR SQUARED TRAJECTORY

	DownRight	DownLeft	UpFrontal	Ours
RMSE	3.3810	0.2459	0.3127	0.0744
Mean	3.1873	0.2221	0.2840	0.0684
Median	3.2201	0.2052	0.2360	0.0633
Std	1.1280	0.1055	0.1309	0.0292
Min	1.1111	0.0646	0.0226	0.0137
Max	5.1173	0.4600	0.6183	0.1807
Sse	81151.2	429.555	694.438	39.3058

Fig. 10. Relative orientation error in the squared trajectory

2) *Pipe Approach Trajectory Evaluation:* During the development of this experiment, a trajectory similar to the one that is performed in the autonomous mission has been carried out. Thus, it is possible to evaluate if the proposed filter improves the results for the use case. Fig. 11 shows the trajectory performed during this experiment.

In contrast to the previous experiment, none of the tracking cameras completely failed. Instead, there was a temporal failure for a fraction of time at the beginning, but the odometry later recovered. Even so, the estimated localization was still better than that obtained by the odometry sources individually. Fig. 12 shows the APE in this trajectory, and Table III covers the main metrics for each sensor and our fused approach.

TABLE III
RESULTS FOR PIPE APPROACH TRAJECTORY

	DownRight	DownLeft	UpFrontal	Ours
RMSE	0.6275	0.1263	0.1983	0.0660
Mean	0.4651	0.1207	0.1910	0.0533
Median	0.2996	0.1202	0.1906	0.0412
Std	0.4212	0.0371	0.0533	0.0388
Min	0.1676	0.0047	0.0282	0.0047
Max	1.6072	0.1854	0.3136	0.2453
Sse	1650.21	66.8622	164.799	18.1259

It has been shown that the proposed solution obtains

Fig. 11. Comparison of the position in the pipe approach trajectory

Fig. 12. APE Evaluation in pipe approach trajectory

sufficiently good results when no sensor fails, and also when the input odometry sources exhibits some drift. This would allow the inspection mission to be performed autonomously and safely.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a complete system for autonomous inspections on pipes. A sensor fusion algorithm for localization that allows the use of redundant sensors has been proposed. This will allow navigation in industrial inspection environments even if a sensor fails accurately. In addition, through the use of the cylinder detection perception algorithm, it will be possible to land on the pipe to perform the necessary measurements.

Once the correct operation of the entire system has been verified in the indoor testbed, the next steps include to

perform inspection missions in outdoor environments. Hence, it is expected to evaluate this system in outdoor environments with the same mock-up rack or other structures. After that, the goal is to perform an inspection in an operating environment within a real refinery, also taking into account the deployment of the crawler that performs measurements on the surface of the pipe.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Anibal Ollero, Guillermo Heredia, Antonio Franchi, Gianluca Antonelli, Konstantin Kondak, Alberto Sanfeliu, Antidio Viguria, J. Ramiro Martínez-de Dios, Francesco Pierri, Juan Cortes, Angel Santamaria-Navarro, Miguel Angel Trujillo Soto, Ribin Balachandran, Juan Andrade-Cetto, and Angel Rodriguez. The aeroarms project: Aerial robots with advanced manipulation capabilities for inspection and maintenance. *IEEE Robotics Automation Magazine*, 25(4):12–23, 2018.
- [2] Rafael Caballero, Jesús Parra, Miguel Trujillo, Francisco Pérez-Grau, Antidio Viguria, and Anibal Ollero. Aerial robotic solution for detailed inspection of viaducts. *Applied Sciences*, 11:8404, 09 2021.
- [3] Francis Idachaba. Monitoring of oil and gas pipelines by use of vtol-type unmanned aerial vehicles. *Oil and Gas Facilities*, 5:47–52, 02 2016.
- [4] Parham Nooralishahi, Clemente Ibarra-Castanedo, Shakeb Deane, Fernando López, Shashank Pant, Marc Genest, Nicolas P. Avdelidis, and Xavier P. V. Maldague. Drone-based non-destructive inspection of industrial sites: A review and case studies. *Drones*, 5(4), 2021.
- [5] Miguel Trujillo, J. Ramiro Martínez-de Dios, Carlos Martín, Antidio Viguria, and Anibal Ollero. Novel aerial manipulator for accurate and robust industrial ndt contact inspection: A new tool for the oil and gas inspection industry. *Sensors*, 19:1305, 03 2019.
- [6] P. Ramon-Soria, A.E. Gomez-Tamm, F.J. Garcia-Rubiales, B.C. Arrue, and A. Ollero. Autonomous landing on pipes using soft gripper for inspection and maintenance in outdoor environments. In *2019 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*, pages 5832–5839, 2019.
- [7] Yuncheng Lu, Zhucun Xue, Gui-Song Xia, and Liangpei Zhang. A survey on vision-based uav navigation. *Geo-spatial information science*, 21(1):21–32, 2018.
- [8] Francisco J Perez-Grau, Ricardo Ragel, Fernando Caballero, Antidio Viguria, and Anibal Ollero. An architecture for robust uav navigation in gps-denied areas. *Journal of Field Robotics*, 35(1):121–145, 2018.
- [9] Ankit Agarwal, Jacob R Crouse, and Eric N Johnson. Evaluation of a commercially available autonomous visual inertial odometry solution for indoor navigation. In *2020 International Conference on Unmanned Aircraft Systems (ICUAS)*, pages 372–381. IEEE, 2020.
- [10] Skydio Inc.
- [11] M. Salvago, F. J. Pérez-Gran, J. Parra, M. A. Trujillo, and A. Viguria. Robust and efficient pose estimation of pipes for contact inspection using aerial robots. In *2021 Aerial Robotic Systems Physically Interacting with the Environment (AIRPHARO)*, pages 1–6, 2021.
- [12] Radu Bogdan Rusu and Steve Cousins. 3D is here: Point Cloud Library (PCL). In *IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, Shanghai, China, May 9–13 2011. IEEE.
- [13] Rohit Chandra, Leo Dagum, David Kohr, Ramesh Menon, Dror Maydan, and Jeff McDonald. *Parallel programming in OpenMP*. Morgan kaufmann, 2001.

- [14] Martin A. Fischler and Robert C. Bolles. Random sample consensus: a paradigm for model fitting with applications to image analysis and automated cartography. *Commun. ACM*, 24:381–395, 1981.
- [15] Lars-Alexander Albrecht. Curvature-based analysis of point clouds. *Fakultät Informatik, Elektrotechnik und Informationstechnik*, 2014.
- [16] R. E. Kalman. A New Approach to Linear Filtering and Prediction Problems. *Journal of Basic Engineering*, 82(1):35–45, 03 1960.
- [17] Michael Grupp. evo: Python package for the evaluation of odometry and slam. <https://github.com/MichaelGrupp/evo>, 2017.